

*International Conference***Himalayan International Transplant Conference, Nepal 2024**

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“The Himalayan International Transplant Conference” was held on December 14 - 15, 2024 at Everest Hotel, Kathmandu, Nepal. The theme for the conference was "Promoting Organ Donation in the Developing World".

At the conference, Ms. Pallavi Kumar, Executive Director, MOHAN Foundation addressed the audience on “Incentives on Organ Donation- A worldview”. Ms Pallavi Kumar's presentation explored various incentive models worldwide to encourage organ donation. It reviewed incentive structures across different countries, including both financial and non-financial models. These incentives range from prioritization on transplant lists, health insurance discounts, funeral expense reimbursements, and tax benefits to controversial financial compensation models. International guidelines, such as those from the World Health Organization (WHO), the Istanbul Declaration, and the Council of Europe, were analysed to provide a regulatory context. Examples from countries like Iran (with a regulated kidney market), the United States, Israel, Singapore, Chile, and India illustrate various models' successes and challenges.

Other esteemed speakers from several countries like Japan, Netherlands, USA, UK covered various topics under the following themes:

- Transplant pathology and immunology
- Organ donation
- Live renal transplantation
- Challenges in transplantation

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